

Prepreg Surface Morphology: A Key Factor in Minimizing Interfacial Air and Interlaminar Voids

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Introduction

Void formation and elimination in laminate

Schematic of interlaminar, intralaminar void formations in laminate

- When insufficient pressure is applied during curing, voids form within the laminate
- Partially impregnated dry tows disappear under vacuum-bag-only curing (i.e., **0.1 MPa** of pressure)^[1]
- Complex techniques are used to eliminate interfacial entrapped airs but all have limitations^[2-6]

Curing with autoclave for high pressure

Schematic of autoclave curing^[10]

Autoclave for Boeing 777X

- Autoclave uses **high pressure** to prevent entrapped air expansion^[2]
- **Limitations** of autoclave:
 - **Capacity** of the autoclave **limits** the size and design of the parts^[4,7]
 - Cost during a curing process accounts for **26%** of the total composite acquisition costs^[8]

Alternative of the autoclave: Out of Autoclave (OoA) prepreg

Schematic of OoA prepreg curing process

- Debulking process is performed after every 1-3 plies for air evacuation^[4]
- Engineered vacuum channels are created **intentionally** for easy air migration^[4]
- **Limitations** of OoA prepreg^[1,3]:
 - For high resin flow, resin composition is altered from autoclave prepreps ⇒ **low reliability**
 - Numerous factors (moisture, out-time, etc) affect void-free curing ⇒ **low stability**

OoA manufacturing strategies for next-generation layup processes

Automated Fiber Placement (AFP)

Filament Winding (FW)

- AFP and FW are automated layup processes using robotics, offering high time and cost efficiency^[9]
- Since debulking is not applicable, **high compaction pressure and fiber tension** are being studied as alternatives in these processes^[10,11]
- However, excessive pressure and tension may cause resin squeeze-out or fiber misalignment^[11]

Relation between prepreg surface and interlaminar void

Optical image of prepreg surface^[1]

Cross-section of laminae^[1]

- Rather than *compressing after layup*, eliminating the **cause of air entrapment** before layup can be more effective
- Recent study suggests that the prepreg surface may be **primary factor** in formation of the interfacial entrapped air and interlaminar void^[1]
- Research topic: relation between **prepreg surface** and **interlaminar void** through experiments

Research objective

To examine relation between **prepreg surface** and **interlaminar void**, these topics need to be understood:

1. Analysis of irregular surface morphology of prepreg
2. Study of correlation between prepreg surface and interlaminar void

Surface morphology of prepreg

Top and bottom side surfaces of prepreg show different textures

Typical unidirectional prepreg roll

Top side prepreg surface

Bottom side prepreg surface

Prepreg cross-section

Height measurement of the prepreg surface

Rough side surface

Smooth side surface

Transverse direction of rough surface has high roughness

PSD curves of rough and smooth side surface

Roughnesses of each surfaces

- Power Spectral Density (PSD) represents the power of **frequencies** composing a surface^[12,13]
- Area under the PSD curve is related to the surface roughness
- Transverse direction of the rough side contributes to difference in roughness between two surfaces

Roughness difference is caused by periodicity of surface valley

PSD curves in transverse direction

Fiber tow width

- Peak in the PSD curve indicates prominence of specific frequency component in the surface
- Rough side surface shows peak, reflecting the **periodic surface valleys**
- Roughness difference between the two surfaces arises from surface valleys at tow-tow junction

Correlation between prepreg surface and interlaminar void

Method for preserving laminae's shape: Cold-ammonia resin solidifying

**Bent laminae due to gravity
at room temperature**

Schematic of cold-ammonia solidifying

- Since resin **deforms** at room temperature, it must be **fixed in shape** for precise imaging
- When **ammonia** and **water vapor** meet amine-curing epoxy, crosslinking is **promoted**^[14]
- Maintaining temperature **below 5 °C** can **minimize** movement of resin^[15]
- Keeping sample for 1 week at 5 °C, then 1 week at room temperature, can **fix** the resin

Lamina surfaces with different roughness forms different interfacial entrapped airs

Micro-CT sample

Micro-CT image sequence of laminae

R: Rough-Rough interface
S: Smooth-Smooth interface

R
S
R
S
R
S
R

- Uncured laminae and cured laminate are stacked with three interface cases:
 - **Rough-Rough**, **Rough-Smooth**, **Smooth-Smooth**
- Dark regions in the micro-CT image sequence represent entrapped airs

Entrapped air and interlaminar void show weak correlation

Rough-Rough, Rough-Smooth, Smooth-Smooth
interfacial entrapped airs

Void removal in each interface cases

- Entrapped air is removed during curing across all types of interfaces
- The greatest amount of removal occurs at the **Rough-Rough** interface

Surface valley affects connectivity of entrapped airs

- In Rough-Rough entrapped air layer, valley induced entrapped airs are **connected** in the layer
- In Smooth-Smooth entrapped air layer, entrapped airs are **not fully connected** each other
- **Air permeability difference** would **affect** void morphology change during curing

Absence of surface valley can reduce interlaminar voids

Entrapped airs in each interface cases

Interlaminar voids in each interface cases

- The Kruskal-Wallis ANOVA is performed to analyze the differences among the three interface types
- **Smooth-Smooth** interface shows clear difference compared to the other two interfaces
- Removing surface valleys can lead to fewer interlaminar voids

Conclusion

Conclusion

- **Valleys** formed at tow-tow junctions are the major difference between both side surfaces of the prepreg
- Interfacial entrapped airs are mainly formed at **valleys** on the prepreg surface
- Minimizing prepreg surface **valleys** can reduce the amount of interlaminar void

Thank you for your attention

